

Appendix 8 Building Sustainable DEI Recommendations Report

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Recommendations on Building A Sustainable AMIA Centered Around Diversity, Equity and Inclusion Practices-A Preliminary Report

Diversity, Equity and Inclusion Task Force

Subcommittee # 3

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Background

The topic of diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) has been in the forefront of 2020. The initiatives around strengthening DEI related structures and policies are rising up, now more than ever. Such efforts are not only limited to USA also gaining attention across the globe.

An essential aspect of these DEI related activities is to ensure that they are long term and sustainable. These DEI related issue are deep rooted, often consequence of a bigger systematic, organizational problems. Addressing them at one point in time is not the real cure of the problem. We need to redesign the infrastructure of the system that could bypass the onset and progression of such DEI related issues.

Objectives

The purpose of this effort is to identify and propose a list of strategic shifts and recommendations. Incorporation of these proposed changes helps equip AMIA and its leaders with an ability to manage, foster, and sustain DEI.

Methods

The current AMIA Strategic Plan is based on three theme/pillars and tasks were assigned to corresponding sub-committees: (i) promote and build the field i.e., to build a diverse AMIA; (ii) empower AMIA members i.e., to build an inclusive AMIA, and (iii) optimize the infra-structure i.e., to build a sustainable AMIA, the third pillar being the topic of main interest here.

Each member of subcommittee # 3 (COT, RR, CJ) independently reviewed the AMIA strategic visioning final report from July 2020. The document illuminates some specific strategic and tactical suggestions based on feedback from AMIA members and other stakeholders. Each of the members came up with a list of the strategic shifts and corresponding recommendations, primarily those stated and retrieved from the Strategic Plan report and few coming from individual experiences as AMIA members of color. Additional recommendations were added as suggested by other subcommittee leads. The list was iteratively revised to remove any duplication of recommended strategic shifts that may have resulted from overlap across three AMIA themes. Each recommendation was also mapped with the three respective DEI pillars/themes and to AMIA Partners (i.e., committees, Working Groups) that could make those actionable. Once the final list was generated, an online survey was conducted with DEI task force members (n=18). The participants were asked to rank the recommendations based on priority such as things that directly impacted DEI and are good initial foundations to get started.

Results

A total of 21 unique strategic shifts (goals) areas were identified. Each proposed shift is described in context of how it can be achieved, possible outcomes, DEI pillars, and which AMIA partners it aligns with that can make the shift actionable. Some of the proposed shifts were applicable across more than one theme i.e., Diverse AMIA (N=8), Inclusive AMIA (N=11), and Sustainable AMIA (N=11). Key Recommendations for the Governance task force (N=5) were also identified. The three top ranked recommendations are: to fortify existing outreach programs with broader scopes and partnerships-Diverse AMIA; to build a multifaceted DEI communication strategy to promote, attract, and advance diversity, and diverse research-Inclusive AMIA and to design a leadership training and mentorship program-Sustainable AMIA.

The next section provided the summary of proposed strategies/shifts (Table 1) followed by detailed description of each shift. The mapping of these recommendations with DEI Themes and AMIA Partners is illustrated in Table 2.

Table 1. Proposed Strategies/Shifts**1. Design a leadership training and mentorship program.**

Goal	How	2020 Baseline	2025 Target	AMIA Partners
1. Nurture leaders and give them the tools they need to manage collective projects responsibly.	Dedicate funds to train AMIA leadership on strategies to promote DEI by experts on DEI for executive leaders such as from the Anti-Defamation League (ADL), and others.	No leadership program.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Create leadership program that places BIPOCs or PEERs into more AMIA leadership positions by 2025. -AMIA leadership equipped to address systematic barriers among PEERs members (e.g., financial, status-related, etc.), -Better define and clarify what AMIA means by DEI -Provide leadership and guidance on how the AMIA environment supports members to bring authentic selves to promote inclusion. -Create a mentorship program that matches BIPOCS PEERs (starting with 0-5 members?) with senior informaticians. 	AMIA Board WIA Membership and Outreach
2. Assess leadership activities and opportunities within AMIA across the membership role continuum from student members to board members (20 hours)	Document AMIA activities that require designated leaders, e.g., AMIA Working Groups, AMIA committees, ad hoc AMIA member-lead and focused projects to identify leadership pool.	Comprehensive list of existing AMIA members who have designated leadership roles.	Maintained and updated list of designated AMIA leaders across the membership spectrum.	AMIA Board Governance Task Force WIA Membership and Outreach Nominations
3. Prioritize leadership roles best positioned to execute DEI efforts within AMIA (100 hours)	Select at least 2 leaders each from at least 4 AMIA leadership roles, that must include the AMIA Board of Directors, AMIA Committee Chair, AMIA Working Group Chair, and Student Group Chair to serve as advisors to inform DEI	Creation of 8-12 member AMIA DEI Leadership Training and Mentoring Advisory Board/Council with creation of charter, goals, and objectives.	Expanded DEI Leadership Training and Mentoring Advisory Council that does not exceed 15 members who have received DEI Leadership and Mentoring Training and document the	AMIA Board Working Groups

	leadership training and mentoring efforts.		facilitated DEI training and mentoring activities within their respective AMIA committee or group.	
4. Collaborate with experienced DEI leadership training and mentoring consultant to develop AMIA (200 hours for development, 8 hours /person for training, 40 hours for follow-up.	Develop DEI Leadership Training and Mentoring process (must decide on a short program (3 hours) or long program full day (7) for DEI Leadership Training and Mentoring Advisory Committee. The degree to which Leadership Training and Mentoring can adapt “train-the-trainer” models so that AMIA leaders can then take ownership for leadership training and mentoring within their respective groups.	Development of AMIA Leadership Training and Mentoring Program for every designated AMIA leader. Identify metrics and outcomes for success to illustrate to AMIA progress of DEI Leadership Training and Mentoring goals.	Require ALL AMIA Board members receive initial DEI leadership training by Sept 2021. Prioritize and roll-out leadership training and mentoring activities across AMIA leadership roles with a plan to reach all leaders by the Fall 2022. Evaluate experience with semi-annual reports to AMIA Board and AMIA membership to address accountability.	AMIA Board Governance Task Force

2. Reconceptualize the Working Groups.

Goal	How	Possible Outcomes	Alignment with DEI Theme/ AMIA Partner	
			DEI Theme	AMIA Partner
To make AMIA Working Groups field-building engines and leadership springboards	Require every AMIA working Group have a DEI plan with SMART goals and objectives that is reviewed by the DEI Sub-Committee.	Better awareness by AMIA DEI leadership to how DEI is addressed within AMIA workgroups.	Sustainable AMIA	Working Group steering Committee, <u>Governance task force</u>

3. Focus on intentional leadership diversity.

Goal	How	Possible Outcomes	Alignment with DEI Theme/ AMIA Partner	
			DEI Theme	AMIA Partner
To promote diverse representation in leadership throughout AMIA.	AMIA to ensure (via charter, policy, by-laws) that each program chair’s nomination, interview, and selection includes a special consideration for applicants that have past experience working with diverse populations that represent the broader AMIA community.	Intentional representation in Board positions to take immediate effect	Sustainable AMIA	Board, Working Group, <u>Governance task force</u> , Elections, Committee, etc.

4. Design and introduce a new online platform to support and collaboration, communication and safe spaces for members.

Goal	How	Possible Outcomes	Alignment with DEI Theme/ AMIA Partner	
			DEI Theme	AMIA Partner
To support Working Group collaboration, networking, conversation, and problem-solving to achieve DEI goals.	Provide an online platform to enable communication and connections among under-represented members. -Ensure the on-line communication tool leverages the best of technology to support written, voice, and video forms of communication.	Use digital communications tools to enhance member engagement, motivation, and opportunities to build a learning community for DEI.	Inclusive AMIA	Member and outreach committee, Communications

5. Design mechanisms for current members to serve as liaisons.

Goal	How	Possible Outcomes	Alignment with DEI Theme/ AMIA Partner	
			DEI Theme	AMIA Partner
To enable member to represent as ambassadors of their respective professional societies	Create a landing page to support liaisons and ambassadors that includes a statement of diversity and inclusion. The statement will provide links to resources and/or ongoing relevant initiatives in AMIA, as well as a summary of highlights on the diversity of our membership. Compensate members who serve as liaisons for AMIA while attending other conferences like AISES or SACNAS	-Clear communication and articulation of how DEI is integral to what AMIA represents by liaisons and ambassadors.	Inclusive AMIA	Communications

6. Fully support the Academic Forum and its members

Goal	How	Possible Outcomes	Alignment with DEI Theme/AMIA Partner	
			DEI Theme	AMIA Partner
To provide necessary support and forums needed for AMIA members through collaborations, e.g., by introducing opportunities for collaboration with the Industry Partnership Council.	Develop a strategy to encourage internship/co-op/fellowship opportunities in collaborations between academic institutions and industry that target and prioritize marginalized or historically excluded members and mentors.	More diverse and inclusive representation of interns and mentors in their respective areas of interest	Inclusive AMIA	Education committee

7. Begin collecting and sharing more precise, transparent data on AMIA's members.

Goal	How	Possible Outcomes	Alignment with DEI Theme/AMIA Partner	
			DEI Theme	AMIA Partner
To collect data on ethnicity, race and gender, as well as on members' country of origin and language.	Digital/electronic survey to members with comprehensive options for members to identify within defined US/global census categories, and options for self-classification of ethnic, cultural, national origin identity, co-develop survey with members.	-Better understand and quantify the distribution of AMIA members across various countries and cultures. -Identify and understand unique needs of AMIA members and if any roadblocks they face. -Analyze, summarize, interpret membership identity data and use to inform decisions and strategic development.	Diverse AMIA	Member and outreach committee

8. Immediately begin a feasibility & business planning process to introduce a larger number of lower-cost virtual conferences.

Goal	How	Possible Outcomes	Alignment with DEI Theme/AMIA Partner	
			DEI Theme	AMIA Partner
Facilitate efficient, affordable, and more inclusive access to AMIA conferences (virtual/face-to-face) with targets to marginalized or historically excluded groups and middle and low-income countries.	Re-evaluate current conferencing policies, pricing models, and advertising practices to identify opportunities to expand outreach to newer communities and targeted DEI priority groups.	-Broader participation of marginalized or historically excluded groups in AMIA conference and educational offerings.	Diverse AMIA	Finance and investment, Member and outreach committee, Working Group steering committee

9. Take steps towards creating an AMIA Assembly, to give all members an ongoing voice in the organization's strategy.

Goal	How	Possible Outcomes	Alignment with DEI Theme/AMIA Partner	
			DEI Theme	AMIA Partner
Improve and increase representation of scholarship, ideas, and input from all members within AMIA to enhance DEI.	To have at least one-member from each AMIA group participate and represent DEI interests across AMIA in a collaborative assembly devoted to DEI within AMIA. Create forums that showcase and highlight DEI efforts, activities and progress through the AMIA DEI Assembly.	Make AMIA the professional home for marginalized or historically excluded communities and create an environment to hear the voice of all in an equitable manner.	Sustainable AMIA	Member and outreach committee, <u>Governance task force</u>

10. Support activities/event promoting collaboration and networking.

Goal	How	Possible Outcomes	Alignment with DEI Theme/AMIA Partner	
			DEI Theme	AMIA Partner
To provide more support for collaboration and networking among members to help facilitate and build connections	Arrange special networking event focusing exclusively on members with diverse backgrounds.	-Stronger connection among members with diverse background -Knowledge and experience sharing -More opportunities for collaborative work at national and international level -Enhanced member experience and value	Diverse AMIA Inclusive AMIA	Member and outreach

11. Provide autonomy and empowerment to all members.

Goal	How	Possible Outcomes	Alignment with DEI Theme/AMIA Partner	
			DEI Theme	AMIA Partner
To empower members to define the program/offering they want and need from AMIA	Have a post conference, DEI-focused, member survey (questions could be added to an existing post-conference survey) For those who want to provide additional feedback, a question could be included to see if they would be willing to respond to a longer DEI-focused survey.	-A more global membership perspectives - A venue to identify members interested in specific DEI topics.	Inclusive AMIA	Member and outreach, Working Groups

12. Develop Workforce base on DEI principles.

Goal	How	Possible Outcomes	Alignment with DEI Theme/AMIA Partner	
			DEI Theme	AMIA Partner
To develop workforce in the informatics field through building the pipeline of professionals from diverse backgrounds	Clarifying the professional landscape and career paths, in context of DEI by providing better descriptions and more knowledge on this	Increased awareness of DEI among current and future informatics professionals	Sustainable AMIA	Member and outreach, Women in AMIA

13. Support and provide venues to other overlooked informatics topics.

Goal	How	Possible Outcomes	Alignment with DEI Theme/AMIA Partner	
			DEI Theme	AMIA Partner
Facilitate growth in public health informatics.	Set priorities for nominating committee to seek candidates from public health informatics and having diverse backgrounds, expertise and unique skill sets (e.g., physicians, epidemiologists, data scientists etc.) - More opportunities e.g., publications, funding, presentations?	- Public health informatics-the new hot topic -Meaningful impact to the communities	Inclusive AMIA	Working Group steering committee, Education

14. Expand the audience.

Goal	How	Possible Outcomes	Alignment with DEI Theme/AMIA Partner	
			DEI Theme	AMIA Partner
To embrace its role in communicating with the general public.	-Expand the audiences through better marketing & communications -Produce lay summaries as white papers of work that could impact policy makers and the public	Being a reliable, transparent and a complete resource to make an impact	Inclusive AMIA	Communications, Membership and Outreach committee, Board

15. Build a multifaceted DEI communication strategy to promote, attract, and advance diversity, and diverse research.

Goal	How	2020 Baseline	2025 Target	AMIA Partners
1. Focus on enhancing diversity in AMIA and the field.	For AMIA supported journals, encourage some focus on the use of informatics to address issues of racism and inequality. In doing so, a strategy that avoids "Special Issue" designation is preferred. Consider highlighting articles that are DEI that are in regular published issues.	The committee will establish methods to gather the data.	The committee will establish methods to gather the data.	AMIA Communications Journals and Publications Membership and Outreach Academic Forum Awards Working Groups
2. Promote diverse research topics and discussions for current and potential AMIA members while avoiding the "Special Issue" designation.	Seek out and request publications from African American, Black, Asian, Hispanic, Latinx, and Native Americans, Indigenous OR PEER researchers who might not otherwise submit their research to AMIA or JAMIA with an emphasis on topics related to the health of marginalized communities. Understanding what these topics are will require surveys and listening sessions.	The committee will establish methods to gather the data.	The committee will establish methods to gather the data.	Communications Journals and Publications Working Groups

16. Make DEI one of the pillars for AMIA success.

Goal	How	Possible Outcomes	Alignment with DEI Theme/AMIA Partner	
			DEI Theme	AMIA Partner
Create a culture of DEI.	All of the above	All of the above	Diverse AMIA Inclusive AMIA Sustainable MAIA	All

17. Fortify existing outreach programs with broader scopes and partnerships.

Goal	How	2020 Baseline	2025 Target	AMIA Partners
1. Provide high school and undergraduate scholars with opportunities to join AMIA and informatics more broadly.	Expand the AMIA High School Scholars (HS Scholars) program to include Historically Black Colleges and Universities (HBCUs), Tribal Colleges and Universities (TCUs), and Hispanic Serving Institutions (HSIs) which are often neglected. Look to AMIA's First Look Program with Women in AMIA to build up the HS Scholars program	Demographic data requested from members who manage the program.	Increase participation in the HS Scholars program by marginalized or historically excluded students across the high school and undergraduate level. The number of undergraduates and community college students in an expanded HS Scholars program.	AMIA High School Scholars Program AMIA First Look Program Academic Forum Membership and Outreach
	Expanded HS Scholars program resources targeted towards early career support, including mentors (a branch off of the other mentorship activities in this model), writing support (applications, grants, papers), a virtual "bulletin board" with opportunities from the community that HS Scholars can apply to.			Number of students who leverage these resources.
2. Targeted outreach, communication, and mutually beneficial partnerships to support HBCUs, TCUs, and HSIs to ensure a pathway of talented Black and Brown people.	Partner with BMI departments DEI efforts (creating AMIA membership/attendance waivers and slots for papers, presentations and posters from students in these DEI programs). Also partnerships to understand approaches to DEI within the AMIA community	Isolated targeted outreach through individualized programs (i.e., AMIA First Look); no systematic approach.	Build relationships within the HBCUs, TCUs and HSIs communities to measure and set a monthly engagement goal. Once baseline data identified, set goals for student attendance at AMIA, for exposure and presentation of content (number of students who attend; content submitted). Number of conference attendees, papers, presentations and posters from these institutions.	Communication Membership and Outreach Academic Forum AMIA First Look Program
	Partnership and outreach to organizations that serve marginalized or historically excluded groups (e.g., Black girls Code, Trans Tech Social Enterprises, SNMA, and marginalized or historically			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of organizations that serve marginalized or historically excluded communities at AMIA booths

	excluded health organizations)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of invited speakers from organizations that serve marginalized or historically excluded communities 	
	Support and provide venues to other overlooked informatics topics (e.g., public health informatics)		Number of calls and target outreach within these informatics fields	
	Design mechanisms for current members to serve as liaisons to conferences that serve marginalized or historically excluded communities in STEM.		Number of liaisons supported	

18. Focus on research impactful for and important to minoritized communities.

Goal	How	Possible Outcomes	Alignment with DEI Theme/AMIA Partner	
			DEI Theme	AMIA Partner
To promote diverse research topics and discussions for current and potential AMIA members while avoiding the “Special Issue” designation.	Seek out and request publications from marginalized or historically excluded researchers who might not otherwise submit their research to AMIA or JAMIA with an emphasis on topics related to the health of minoritized communities. Understanding what these topics are will require surveys and listening sessions.	Earlier exposure to informatics and what AMIA has to offer.	Inclusive AMIA Sustainable AMIA	Health Disparities Communications journals and publications

19. Diversity in programming, events and conferences.

Goal	How	Possible Outcomes	Alignment with DEI Theme/AMIA Partner	
			DEI Theme	Working Group
Diversify the network of AMIA partnerships to include external organizations to augment DEI efforts.	AMIA to create strategic partnerships with similar, yet more inclusive organizations <i>i.e. Black Girls Code, Trans Tech Social Enterprises, Blacks in Technology, .etc.</i> For example, joint calls for papers, special JAMIA issues, lunch time web series or panel discussions, etc.	Increase exposure and access of groups that have traditionally not engaged in AMIA activities Increase membership Provide diversity in mentorship for student members Improved programming and content for members	Diverse AMIA	Member and outreach committee, High School scholars
Address Student Volunteer Program		Address Equity		

20. Address systemic racism and health equity.

Goal	How	Possible Outcomes	Alignment with DEI Theme/AMIA Partner	
			DEI Theme	AMIA Partner
Recommend formal subcommittee be established under the DEI Committee to further examine systemic racism and health equity.	Systemic racism and health equity. There is an opportunity and need for AMIA to lead in this space.	Create subcommittee focused on systematic racism and health equity.	Diverse AMIA	N/A

21. Recruitment and retainment of executive DEI AMIA staff member.

Goal	How	Possible Outcomes	Alignment with DEI Theme/AMIA Partner	
			DEI Theme	AMIA Partner
Create a full-time position who is responsible for all AMIA DEI oversight.	AMIA to hire executive level career staff members who are responsible and accountable to AMIA membership and board to ensure equity, inclusion and diversity are propagated throughout the AMIA organization and events.	Less dependence on Working Groups and Task Forces.	Diverse AMIA Inclusive AMIA Sustainable AMIA	N/A

Table 2: Alignment of proposed strategies with DEI Themes AMIA Partners

AMIA Strategic Plan Core 1: Promote and Build the Field		AMIA Strategic Plan Core 2: Empower our Members		AMIA Strategic Plan Core 3: Optimize Infrastructure	
DEI Task Force Target 1: Make AMIA Diverse– Subcommittee #1		DEI Task Force Target 2: Make AMIA Inclusive– Subcommittee #2		DEI Task Force Target 3: Make AMIA’s DEI Sustainable– Subcommittee #3	
Recommendations (N=8)	AMIA Partner	Recommendations (N=11)	AMIA Partner	Recommendations (N=11)	AMIA Partner
Begin collecting and sharing more precise, transparent data on AMIA’s members.	Member and Outreach committee	Design and introduce a new online platform to support and collaboration, communication and safe spaces for members.	Member and outreach committee, Communications	Design a leadership training and mentorship program	Education committee
Immediately begin a feasibility & business planning process to introduce a larger number of lower-cost virtual conferences.	Finance and investment committee, Member and outreach committee, Working Group steering committee	Design mechanisms for current members to serve as liaisons	Communications	Reconceptualize the Working Groups	Working Group steering committee, <u>Governance task force</u>
Support activities/event promoting collaboration and networking	Member and outreach committee	Fully support the Academic Forum and its members	Education committee	Take steps towards creating an AMIA Assembly, to give all members an ongoing voice in the organization’s strategy.	Member and outreach committee, <u>Governance task force</u>
Make DEI one of the pillars for AMIA success	All	Support activities/event promoting collaboration and networking	Member and outreach committee	Develop workforce base on DEI principles	Membership and outreach, Women in AMIA
Fortify existing outreach programs with broader scopes and partnerships	High school scholars	Provide autonomy and empowerment to all members	Membership and outreach committee, Working Groups	Make DEI one of the pillars for AMIA success	All

Build a multifaceted DEI communication strategy to promote, attract, and advance diversity, and diverse research	Health disparities, Communications, Journals and publications	Build a multifaceted DEI communication strategy to promote, attract, and advance diversity, and diverse research	Health Disparities, Communications, Journals and publications	Focus on intentional leadership diversity.	Board, Working Group, <u>Governance task force</u> , Election committee, etc.
Diversity in programming, events and conferences	Member and Outreach committee, Communications, Journals and publications	Support and provide venues to other overlooked informatics topics	Working Group steering committee, Education committee	Fortify existing outreach programs with broader scopes and partnerships	High school scholars
Recruitment and retainment of executive DEI AMIA staff member	Member and outreach committee, High school scholars	Expand the audience	Communications, Membership and Outreach committee, Board	Build a multifaceted DEI communication strategy to promote, attract, and advance diversity, and diverse research	Health disparities, Communications, Journals and publications
		Make DEI one of the pillars for AMIA success	All	Focus on research impactful for and important to minoritized communities	Health Disparities, Communications journals and publications
		Focus on research impactful for and important to minoritized communities	Health disparities, Communications, Journals and publications	Address systemic racism and health equity	Board, Working Group, <u>Governance task force</u> ,
		Recruitment and retainment of executive DEI AMIA staff member		Recruitment and retainment of executive DEI AMIA staff member	Board, <u>Governance task force</u> ,